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BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

UNVEILING PORTUGAL'S ROLE: THE GATEWAY TO ILLICIT ARMS TRADE IN EUROPE.

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Policy Statement

Portugal's pivotal role in Europe's illicit arms trade is underscored by its strategic geographic location and maritime connections. Lax regulatory frameworks exacerbate the ease with which illegal arms are trafficked through the country. As a member of the European Union, Portugal presents challenges and opportunities to combat this transnational threat. Urgent action necessitates strengthened legislation, enhanced enforcement, and international collaboration. Understanding and addressing Portugal's role is essential for curbing the destabilizing effects of illicit arms trade and upholding regional security within Europe.

Background

The 2023 Global Organized Crime Index^[1] appoints Portugal as a central hub for drug trafficking, human trafficking, and smuggling for labor exploitation. Still, perhaps Portugal's government and the European Union should pay attention to the other major threat represented: Arms Trafficking.

Due to its pivotal position from the geographic perspective, Portugal holds a central geostrategic position for arms trafficking by being the most Western country in mainland Europe, attracting the attention of illegal arms dealers that wish to spread their commerce in Western Europe is already marked by mafia/organized crime and human trafficking, especially for labor. Although Portugal has been marked stable by the Ocidex in the matter, drug and organized crime have ranked higher, begging the question of why the arms industry is falling behind.

As Mercado (2020) ^[2] explains, there is a symbiotic relationship between drugs, organized crime, and arms trafficking, creating a cluster that pushes the other sectors to evolve and grow. As the different sectors grow, there is a real possibility that the arms sector will also increase. In the Portuguese scenario, organized crime is already installed as a hub for cocaine commerce in Europe. With cedes of other organized crime in South America, Africa, and recently founded Chinese squadrons, there is still a low rise in the arms sector that may constitute a problem unseen, like drugs and human

trafficking, especially in the Alentejo region. The first issue with dealing with arms trafficking in the Portuguese scenario is that we had little data before 2017 about the number of weapons and the type of guns and arms we were dealing with. The process of identifying a weapon started around the 1990s, but the data lacked the precision to quantify and qualify the origin and typology of the armament.

Findings

According to the Regional Analysis Report from UNODC of 2020, Portugal had in 2017 a total of 6,754 weapons seized, and 51% of those were classified as Unknown.

This raises the issue of Portugal's weapon industry's prior status and illegal commercialization justified by homemade weapons and ammunition before the 1990s, as well as the customizations and modifications of the standard gun and keeping it off the records. This later correlates with the report made by UNODC about the typology of guns marked Unknown, contributing to the imprecision in clarifying Portugal's initial scenario about the topic since the unknown guns can derive from modified pistols to modified automatic weapons.

This affects the starting point of the discussion by two factors: a) the illegal arms industry benefits from this loophole by creating a grey area of the scenario presented, and b) The European Union, NGOs, and civil society institutions will not be presented with the proper data to allocate resources, money, and new studies to reduce the problem. Although the provision given by the UNODC is that Portugal should remain stable in the matter, there is still little to know about the answers to this first scenario.

Recommendations

Assuming that there are way more weapons and illegal arms evolve, we need to ensure better control of arms trafficking. Portugal must adopt a multifaceted strategy that includes strengthening legislation to criminalize illicit arms activities by collaborating internationally with organizations like Interpol and Europol, as well as civil society, to keep track of this information and fill the gap between traditional politics sometimes made in Brussels. As the Resolution of the United Nations Convention states

“Acknowledging the valuable contributions, where appropriate and useful for academia, the private sector, and civil society in addressing some of the challenges posed by and the impact of the illicit manufacturing of and trafficking in firearms.” [3]

This statement reiterates that there is a need for contributions from NGOs and civil society that harness information more quickly and update it, which is fundamental to solving and anticipating some problems. In the information field, sharing, best practice exchange, and cooperation with UNODOC and UN Firearms Protocol bolster the legal frameworks to enhance border control. Investing in the use of advanced technology prevents illegal arms movement by facilitating the migration of data and cross-information between organizations to access better and prevent unlawful commerce.

This transparency can be an excellent example of combating the arms trade. A good example is the NCIS initiative,[4] which uses and trains AI to analyze better and train the intelligence to make this cross data a tool to keep track of the incoming track by filtering news gathered by keywords online. As arms trafficking uses more technology and amplifies the means and ways, we must evolve even faster by allocating resources to central government and non-traditional politics like organizations and civil society. Public awareness campaigns also encourage reports of suspicious activities, aiding law enforcement efforts.

Conclusions

Portugal's strategic geographic location and maritime connections underscore its pivotal role in Europe's illicit arms trade. However, the lack of knowledge about the starting point of the matter allied with lax regulatory frameworks exacerbates the ease with which illegal arms are trafficked throughout the country. As a member of the European Union and door of entry of Europe, Portugal faces both challenges and opportunities in combating this transnational threat. Urgent action requires strengthened legislation, enhanced enforcement, and international collaboration. Understanding and addressing Portugal's role is crucial for curbing the destabilizing effects of illicit arms trade and upholding regional security within Europe.

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[1] ©2023 OCINDEX.NET/COUNTRY/PORTUGAL

[2] ARMS TRAFFICKING AND ORGANIZED CRIME 2022

[3] "Strengthening international cooperation against the illicit manufacturing of and trafficking in firearms, their parts and components and ammunition, 2008, p.4.

[4] For consulting the NCIS website: [NCIS, Nautical Crime Investigation Services Corp \(ncis-tech.com\)](#)

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